

The red patch crab spider *Thomisus australis* Comellini, 1957 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT: *Thomisus australis* Comellini, 1957 was first described from Champagne Castle in the Drakensberg Mountains of South Africa. Presently, it is widely distributed in eastern and southern Africa. Their presence in South Africa is discussed, with notes on lifestyle, colour variation, and morphology based on live photographs.

Keywords: biodiversity, conservation, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Thomisus* Walckenaer, 1805, is represented by 142 species, of which 16 occur in South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2025). During surveys for the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), primarily by sweeping and beating vegetation, large numbers of *Thomisus* specimens have been collected (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Sixteen species are presently recorded from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020a).

A SANSA species page series was initiated after the release of the Photo Identification Guides to provide additional information on species, mainly to show the range of colour variations to be expected. The *Thomisus* species page series included species such as *T. blandus* Karsch (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Uys, 2025), *T. kalaharinus* Lawrence (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023), *T. granulatus* Karsch and *T. spiculosus* (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022), *T. scrupeus* (Simon), Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2023), and *T. stenningi* (in this issue).

In this paper, we look at *T. australis* Comellini, 1957. The species was described from Champagne Castle in the Drakensberg Mountains of South Africa. Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983) revised the *Thomisus* species of southern Africa and examined collections from Burundi, Democratic Republic of Congo, Lesotho, Malawi, Mozambique, South Africa and Tanzania. This resulted in the recognition of the species *T. mossambicus* Comellini, 1957, *T. mossambicus weidneri* Comellini, 1957, and *T. drakensbergensis* Comellini, 1959 as junior synonyms of *T. australis*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The specimens sampled during the SANSA surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria. As part of SANSA, requests were made for photographs for the SANSA Virtual Museum and the photographs used in this article were obtained through this initiative. Additional images were also added from iNaturalist (Figs 10–12 & 15–16).

TAXONOMY

Thomisus australis Comellini, 1957

Thomisus australis Comellini, 1957: 6 (m); Comellini, 1959: 112 (f); Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983: 30 (mf, S of *Thomisus drakensbergensis*, *T. mossambicus* and *T. mossambicus weidneri*); Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1988: 435 (mf); Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020: 40 (mf).

Thomisus mossambicus Comellini, 1957: 20 (f).

Thomisus mossambicus weidneri Comellini, 1957: 20 (f).

Thomisus drakensbergensis Comellini, 1959: 114 (f).

Figures 1–3. *Thomisus australis*. 1. Female from Wakefield. 2. Female eye pattern. 3. Male from Cape Town. Credits: Peter Webb.

Figures 4–8. *Thomisus australis*. 4–5. Female epigyne. 6–8. Male palp. Credits: 4 & 6. After Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983. 5. Ruan Booyesen. 7–8 Jan Bosselaers.

Diagnostic characters: Female. Size TL 6–7 mm. Carapace yellowish, with two mediolateral darker bands (Fig. 1); eyes with a reddish-brown triangular pattern with a narrow white border as viewed from the front (Figs 2 & 14). Abdomens vary from yellowish-white, sometimes with faint transverse bands (Figs 1 & 15), to creamy white. Females can change colour from white (Fig. 12) to yellow (Fig. 15). However, usually the reddish triangular pattern between the anterior eyes is always present. Legs are the same colour as the carapace. The epigynum of the female is large and horseshoe-shaped (Figs 4 & 5). **Male.** Size TL 3–4 mm. Carapace yellowish brown with dark mediolateral bands (Figs 3 & 11); integument with scattered tubercles bearing short erect setae (Fig. 10); eyes with triangular pattern (Fig. 9) sometimes less distinct than in females (Fig. 10). Abdomen ovate; yellowish with faint bands (Figs 9 & 11); sometimes with bands reddish (Fig. 9); clothed with numerous dark spiniform setae (Fig. 11). Front legs with femora varying from greenish (Figs 10 & 11) to reddish brown (Fig. 3); rest of segments with dark and paler brown bands (Fig. 11). Palp with short firmly pointed embolus (Figs 6 & 7) and dark tubercle and seta on the retrolateral side of tibia (Figs 6–8).

Remarks: *Thomisus australis* bears a close resemblance to *T. dalmasi*, *T. stenningi* and *T. kalaharinus* in size, shape and colour but differs from them in the shape of the genitalia.

LIFESTYLE

Thomisus australis is free-living on plants, sampled mainly from flowers, grass, and the herb layer, using sweeping and beating techniques. The species feeds on a wide range of mites and insects (Fig. 12) and, during SANSA surveys, have been sampled from peach orchards and tomatoes (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013). The females were sampled from December to April, and the males from November to May (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983).

Figures 9–11. *Thomisus australis*. 9. Male dorsal view from Fernkloof Nature Reserve. 10–11. Male from Wakkerstroom. Credits: 9. Jan Bosselaers. 10–11. Angus Burns.

Figure 12. *Thomisus australis* female feeding on a fly. Credits: N.T. Moolman.

DISTRIBUTION

The species was originally described from South Africa in 1957 but is now recorded from several countries in the Afrotropical Region.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Burundi, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Malawi, Mozambique, Tanzania, Lesotho, South Africa. Additional country records based on iNaturalist observations include Botswana, Eswatini, Kenya, Uganda and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: (Fig. 16). *Thomisus australis* has a wide distribution throughout South Africa absent from North West and with lower numbers in the Free State and Northern Cape. This species has been sampled from the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024a), Grassland, Savanna (Fig. 16), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Thicket biomes but seems to be less common in the more arid ones. The species was also sampled from pecan orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

In the Eastern Cape it was listed from the Amathole Mountains (Haddad *et al.*, 2023) and the Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020b). In the Free State it is listed from the Golden Gate National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz, 2024) and in Gauteng from the Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2024). From the Limpopo Province they were sampled from the Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019), Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2016), Marakele National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021) and the Soutpansberg (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024c). In the Western Cape protected in the De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2009), Garden Route Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024b) and Table Mountain National Park (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2024).

Figures 13–16. *Thomisus australis* female. 13. From Wakefield. 14. From Hoedspruit. 15. From Witsieshoek. 16. Eye pattern. Credits: 13–14 Peter Webb. 15. Felix Riegel. 16. Wolf Avni.

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